

Diagnosis of Paediatric Inguino Scrotal Pathologies /Abnormalities by Ultrasonography – A Pictorial Presentation of Case SeriesParesh Bhowmik¹, Akash Shikar Debbarma²¹Senior Resident, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Agartala Government Medical College & GBPH, Agartala²Postgraduate Trainee, Department of Radio-diagnosis, Agartala Government Medical College & GBPH, Agartala

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Abstract:

Ultrasonography (USG) is the preferred imaging method for the evaluation of paediatric inguino scrotal pathologies. It is an easily available imaging modality. It is also cost effective & non-hazardous for children as there is no risk of radiation or any other side effects. Ultrasonography is done to diagnose and evaluate paediatric inguinoscrotal pathologies /abnormalities, such as inguinal hernia, hydrocele, testicular microlithiasis, undescended testis, epididymo-orchitis etc. Over the past few decades, ultrasonography techniques have been developed tremendously - starting from colour Doppler, spectral analysis, contrast USG to 3D & 4D imaging. Here we are presenting few cases where diagnosis was made by ultrasonography & Colour Doppler.

1. Right encysted hydrocele which was diagnosed by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.
2. Right undescended testis (located in the proximal part of right inguinal canal) with bilateral testicular microlithiasis, diagnosis was made by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.
3. A reducible right inguinal hernia with left sided infantile hydrocele, diagnosed by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.
4. Right focal epididymitis diagnosis was made by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.
5. Funicular type of right spermatic cord hydrocele which was diagnosed by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.
6. A small reducible right inguinal hernia diagnosed by ultrasonography and colour Doppler.

Ultrasonography is a type of radiological examination where sound waves are used to produce picture of different organs of body and their pathologies. Colour Doppler is used to further characterize any pathology.

Keywords: Ultrasonography and colour Doppler, encysted hydrocele, undescended testis, testicular microlithiasis, focal epididymitis diagnosis, inguinal hernia, funicular type of spermatic cord hydrocele.

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Introduction

Ultrasonography is the preferred imaging method for the evaluation of paediatric inguino scrotal pathologies. It is an easily available imaging modality. It is also cost effective & non-hazardous for children as there is no risk of radiation or any other side effect.

Ultrasonography is done to diagnose and evaluate paediatric inguinoscrotal pathologies /abnormalities, such as inguinal hernia, hydrocele, testicular microlithiasis, undescended testis, epididymo-orchitis, testicular mass etc.

Over the past few decades, ultrasonography techniques have been developed tremendously - starting from colour Doppler, spectral analysis, contrast USG to 3D & 4D USG imaging. Here we are presenting a few cases where diagnosis was

made possible by ultrasonography & Colour Doppler.

Case Series:

Case 1: A 29 days old male child was brought by his parents with the complains of swelling in the right inguinal region. It is not increasing in size with crying and is not painful. They noticed it 10days back. He is the only child. His bowel and bladder habits are normal. His development is normal for age. The child is exclusively breast fed.

On examination, all reflexes are within normal limits. Pulse rate was 88/min. Systemic examination of cardiovascular system, respiratory system; central nervous system & abdomen were within normal limits.

Local examination reveals- a swelling in right inguinal region. It was not reducible and not increasing in size on crying. It was cystic consistency on palpation and not tender.

His routine blood and urine examination were within normal limit. His ultrasonography examination showed-anechoic collection without

any internal septations/debris measuring approx (2.26 cm x 0.84 cm) in the mid part of right inguinal canal. It was separated from and located above the right testis and the epididymis without communication with the peritoneal cavity. It did not increase in size on straining. No bowel loop seen in its content. On colour Doppler show – no colour flow was seen within the collection.

Figure 1: Collection without any internal septation/debris measuring approx 2.26 cm x 0.84 cm in the mid part of right inguinal canal. It was separated from and located above the right testis and the epididymis without communication with the peritoneal cavity.

Diagnosis:

Right encysted hydrocele.

D/D:

Inguinal hernia: It is increased in size with cry if not obstructed and have communication with peritoneal cavity. Some solid content including bowel loops may be seen in its contents. On colour Doppler – colour flow can be seen in solid content.

Hydrocele of canal of Nuck: It occurs in females.

Case 2: An 1 years 8 months old male child was brought by his parents with the complains of right testis not found in right hemiscrotum & a small mass like structure in the right inguinal region. They noticed it last year. He is the second born child. His bowel and bladder habits are normal. His development is normal for age. The child is on a mixed diet of breast milk & home-made food. There are four members in his family and all are apparently healthy. On examination all his reflexes

were within normal limit. Fair nutrition, pulse rate was 84/min. His systemic examination of central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system & abdomen were within normal limit.

Local examination reveals- a soft tissue mass in right inguinal region. It was solid on palpation and not tender. It was not reducible and not increases in size with cry.

His routine blood and urine examination were within normal limit. Ultrasonography examination show -right testis is located in the proximal part of right inguinal canal. It is heterogeneous in echotexture. Multiple tiny echogenic structures are seen in the right testis. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen. Left testis is located within left scrotum .It is heterogeneous in echotexture. Multiple tiny echogenic structures with weak posterior acoustic shadow are seen in the left testis. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen.

Figure 2: A.right testis is located in the proximal part of right inguinal canal.

It is heterogeneous in echotexture. Multiple tiny echogenic structures are seen in the right testis. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen. B. Left is located within left scrotum. It is heterogeneous in echotexture.

Figure1: Ultrasonography examination show -right testis is located in the proximal part Figure2: Ultrasonography examination show (A)-right testis is located in the proximal part of right inguinal canal. It is heterogeneous in echotexture. Multiple tiny echogenic structures are seen in the right testis. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen.(B) Left testis is located within left scrotum .It is heterogeneous in echotexture. Multiple tiny echogenic structures with weak posterior acoustic shadow are seen in the left testis. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen.

Diagnosis: Right undescended testis (located in the proximal part of right inguinal canal) with bilateral testicular microlithiasis.

Differential diagnosis:

Right Inguinal hernia: It is increased in size with cry if not obstructed and have communication with peritoneal cavity. Some solid content including bowel loops may be seen in its contents. On colour Doppler – colour flow can be seen in sold content.

Case 3: A 10 years old male child was presented with on and off fever and severe pain in the right hemiscrotum which was red and swollen since 1 week. He also had increased frequency and urge to urinate with burning sensation while urination.

On examination his all reflexes are within normal limit. Fair nutrition, pulse rate was 80/min. His systemic examination of central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system &abdomen were within normal limit.

Local examination reveals- a tender inflamed enlarged right hemiscrotum. The left hemiscrotum was normal. Bilateral inguinal regions were normal.

His ultrasonography examination showed - Thickened and oedematous head of right epididymis (measuring approx.- Head- 1.52cm x 1.43cm, tail -1.13 cm x 0.69cm) with heterogeneous echotexture. On colour Doppler study -increased colour flow was seen. The left epididymis was normal in size, shape and

echotexture with normal colour flow pattern on colour Doppler. Bilateral testes were normal in size, shape, echotexture and volume with normal colour flow pattern on colour Doppler. There was no evidence of varicocele or hydrocele and both the spermatic cords were normal.

Figure 3: Thickened and oedematous head of right epididymis with heterogeneous echotexture.

Diagnosis-

Right Focal Epididymitis.

D/D

Adenomatoid tumours of the scrotum:

Adenomatoid tumours of the scrotum are benign, solid extra testicular lesions that can originate from the epididymis, tunica vaginalis, or spermatic cord (90% derived from the funiculus).

Epidemiology: They are the most common extra testicular neoplasm, and most common tumour of the epididymis, and occur more often in the lower pole than in the upper pole by a ratio of 4:1.

Clinical presentation: Usually an incidental finding, adenomatoid tumours manifest as a small (usually under 2 cm), painless scrotal mass, with the majority diagnosed in patients aged 20-50 years. They are typically unilateral and occur more frequently on the left side.

Ultrasound:

- well-defined, usually oval extra testicular mass with variable echogenicity although most are isoechoic to the epididymis
- usually solid although can be completely cystic

- range in size from a few millimetres to a few centimetre

Case 4: An 1 year 2 months 5 days old male infant was brought by his parents with complaints of a lump in the scrotum since weeks.

The parents denied any history of testicular trauma. The lump was not recurrent but had exhibited growth. However, it did not exhibit growth when the patient was active during the day or during bouts of crying.

On examination his all reflexes are within normal limit. He was exclusively breast-fed. Pulse rate was 92/min.

His systemic examination of central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system & abdomen were within normal limit.

Local examination reveals- the right hemiscrotum was larger than the left hemiscrotum. On palpation the lump was well-defined, soft, fluctuant and oval. There was no tenderness and trans illumination test was positive. On auscultation, no bowel sounds were heard.

His ultrasonography examination showed - Evidence of anechoic collection without any

internal septation/debris (measuring approx 3.39cm x 1.29cm x 0.98cm and volume-2.24cc) along the spermatic cord of right inguinal canal.

It was separated from testis and epididymis inferiorly and communicating with the peritoneal cavity through an open internal inguinal ring.

It did not increase in size on strain. No bowel loop was seen in its content. On colour Doppler

examination – No colour flow was seen within the collection.

Bilateral testes and epididymis were normal in size, shaped and echotexture with normal colour flow pattern on colour Doppler. No evidence of varicocele or scrotal wall thickening was seen.

Diagnosis-Funicular type of right spermatic cord hydrocele

Figure 4: Anechoic collection without any internal septation/debris (measuring approx 3.39cm x 1.29cm x 0.98cm and volume-2.24cc) along the spermatic cord of right inguinal canal. It was separated from testis and epididymis inferiorly and communicating with the peritoneal cavity through an open internal inguinal ring. It did not increase in size on strain. No bowel loop was seen in its content. On colour Doppler examination – No colour flow was seen within the collection.

Diagnosis:

Right Funicular type of spermatic cord hydrocele.

Differential diagnosis:

Right Inguinal hernia: It is increased in size with cry if not obstructed and have communication with peritoneal cavity. Some solid content including bowel loops may be seen in its contents. On colour Doppler – colour flow can be seen in sold content.

Case 5:

A 10month old female child was brought by her parents with the complaints of a lump near the groin area on right side since 5 months.

The child was irritable most of times and the lump would get bigger during crying.

The lump could be pressed back into the abdomen and would bulge out again as the child would cry.

On examination her developmental milestones and reflexes are within normal limit. She was exclusively breast-fed. Pulse rate was 96/min. Her systemic examination of central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system & abdomen were within normal limit. Local examination reveals-a soft fluctuant swelling in the right groin region. The swelling was reducible completely and would protrude out on crying. On auscultation, no bowel sounds were heard. Her ultrasonography examination showed -Evidence of a small, ill defined, heterogeneously hypoechoic structure, measuring approx (1.92cm x 1.17cm) is protruded through the right inguinal canal on strain & return to the abdominal cavity on rest.

No bowel gas shadow/ peristaltic movement is seen within the content. On colour Doppler study-minimal colour flow is seen. Left inguinal region is seen normal. No hernia is seen in left inguinal region.

Figure 5: a small, ill defined, heterogeneously hypoechoic structure, measuring approx. (1.92cm x 1.17cm) is protruded through the right inguinal canal on strain & return to the abdominal cavity on rest. No bowel gas shadow/ peristaltic movement is seen within the content. On colour Doppler study- minimal colour flow is seen.

Diagnosis-

A small right sided reducible inguinal hernia.

Differential diagnosis:

Right Funicular type of spermatic cord hydrocele: Evidence of anechoic collection without any internal septation/debris along the spermatic cord of right inguinal canal. It was separated from testis and epididymis inferiorly and communicating with the peritoneal cavity through an open internal inguinal ring. It did not increase in size on strain. No bowel loop was seen in its content. On colour Doppler examination – No colour flow was seen within the collection.

Case 6:

A 7months old male child was brought by his parents with complaints of a lump in the groin region on right side and another swelling in the left scrotum since 3 months. The parents did not give any history of testicular trauma. The lump on the right groin region was soft and could be pressed back into the abdomen. It would increase as the child would cry. The swelling in the left scrotum was soft and could not be pressed back into the abdomen and did not increase in size with crying.

On examination all his developmental milestones and reflexes are within normal limit. He was

exclusively breast-fed. Pulse rate was 96/min. His systemic examination of central nervous system, cardiovascular system, respiratory system & abdomen were within normal limit. Local examination reveals- the swelling in the right groin region was soft and fluctuant and could be reduced into the abdominal cavity. It would protrude out and increase in size upon crying. On auscultation, bowel sounds were heard.

The left hemiscrotum was larger than the right hemiscrotum. On palpation the lump was well-defined, soft, fluctuant and oval. There was no tenderness and trans illumination test was positive. On auscultation, no bowel sounds were heard.

His ultrasonography examination showed - anechoic collection without any internal septation measuring approx (3.46 cm x 1.86 cm x 1.09cm=3.65cc) is seen in the distal part of left inguinal canal and left side of scrotum around the left testis. It is not increased in size on strain. No bowel loop seen in its content. On Colour Doppler study - no colour flow is seen within the collection. Evidence of a small, ill-defined heterogeneously echogenic structure, measuring approx. (3.21cm x 1.59cm) is protruded through the right inguinal canal on strain & return to the abdominal cavity on rest. Bowel gas shadow is seen within the structure. On colour Doppler study- colour flow is seen.

Figure 6: (A) a small, ill-defined heterogeneously echogenic structure, measuring approx. (3.21cm x 1.59cm) is protruded through the right inguinal canal on strain & return to the abdominal cavity on rest. Bowel gas shadow is seen within the structure. On colour Doppler study- colour flow is seen.(B)anechoic collection without any internal septation measuring approx (3.46 cm x 1.86 cm x 1.09cm=3.65cc) is seen in the distal part of left inguinal canal and left side of scrotum around the left testis. It is not increased in size on strain. No bowel loop seen in its content. On Colour Doppler study - no colour flow is seen within the collection.

Diagnosis-

Right sided reducible inguinal hernia with left sided infantile hydrocele.

Differential diagnosis:

Bilateral Funicular type of spermatic cord hydrocele.

Evidence of anechoic collections without any internal septation/debris along the spermatic cord of bilateral inguinal canal. They were separated from testis and epididymis inferiorly and communicating with the peritoneal cavity through an open internal inguinal ring. They did not increase in size on strain. No bowel loop was seen in their contents. On colour Doppler examination – No colour flow was seen within the collections.

Discussion

Ultrasound is an essential imaging technique for examining inguino-scrotal masses due to its non-invasive nature, capability to differentiate between various tissues, and high-resolution imaging. Given the complexity of the scrotum and inguinal regions,

ultrasound provides rapid, real-time imaging that is crucial for accurate diagnosis and management [1]. This imaging modality is excellent at distinguishing between solid and cystic masses. Cystic lesions, such as hydrocele or spermatoceles, appear anechoic on ultrasound and usually have smooth, well-defined edges. Conversely, solid masses, including tumors, often present with varied echogenicity and irregular shapes. Identifying this distinction is vital for determining the appropriate course of action, as solid masses might need biopsy or surgical intervention, while cystic lesions may be managed conservatively or with drainage [2]. Ultrasound also helps locate a mass precisely within the scrotum or inguinal canal, which is crucial for differentiating between testicular and extra testicular masses. For example, epididymal cysts and tumors are generally extra testicular and have distinct ultrasound characteristics compared to testicular tumors. Additionally, it assists in identifying whether a mass is intra-abdominal or a hernia extending into the scrotum [3]. Doppler ultrasound further enhances the evaluation by examining blood flow within the mass. Increased

vascularity can suggest malignancy or inflammation, whereas a lack of blood flow might indicate a benign condition. This functional assessment aids in differentiating conditions like testicular torsion, which is marked by reduced or absent blood flow, from other conditions with increased vascularity [4].

Ultrasound is also vital for guiding further diagnostic and treatment steps. It can accurately locate a mass before surgery and, in some cases, guide fine needle aspiration or biopsy. This precision reduces surgical risks and ensures targeted treatment [5]. Despite its many advantages, ultrasound has some limitations. It might not always clearly differentiate between benign and malignant lesions, especially in cases where solid masses have similar echogenicity. In such situations, additional imaging techniques like CT or MRI, or histopathological analysis, may be necessary.

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